

TO ANALYZE THE EUTROPHICATION PROCESS AND ITS EFFECTS ON INTERACTING AQUATIC POPULATION- FEM AND ANN

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Abstract

In the aquatic environment, the level of eutrophication is increasing. It is critical to precisely assess eutrophication in order to treat it appropriately. Moreover, the assessment of eutrophication has not been satisfactorily resolved since it is fraught with uncertainties. Hence, we have considered a lake that has been eutrophicated due to an overabundance of algae and other biological species induced by nutrient flow from home drainage, water runoff, and other sources, as well as nutrients created from detritus. The variables bilinear interactions such as cumulative nutrient concentrations, algal (phytoplankton) and fish population densities, detritus density, and dissolved oxygen concentration are addressed. ANN model has been established by utilizing the pertinent parameters data set attained by finite element method. Here, 80% of the data used in the development of the multilayer perceptron network, 10% of the data has been used for training the model and 10% for testing. The study's outcomes revealed that the built ANN models can generate accurate predictions.

Keywords: Eutrophication Process; Artificial Neural Networking; Finite Element Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The conversion of most of the earth's land surface to agricultural or urban area has had a significant impact on nutrient fluxes at all sizes, from local to global. Natural ecosystems, on the whole, do a good job of conserving nutrients and storing organic matter. Such conservation mechanisms are compromised in all agricultural systems, and management raises nutrient inputs above natural levels. Together, these changed ecological traits result in enormous nutrient leakage into rivers. Even when contemporary sewage treatment equipment is used, humans concentrate nutrients from meals and discharge excreta, resulting in massive nutrient

fluxes in densely populated places. As a result, eutrophication of many of the world's waterways has become a widespread and costly concern for human health and amenity, water supply and environmental conservation. By affecting biodiversity, trophic structure, and biogeochemical cycling, eutrophication has a significant impact on aquatic ecosystems. The primary concerns in water quality management in recent decades have been eutrophication and micropollutant pollution of lakes and rivers. Both issues have been the subject of substantial study and modelling, but they have typically been dealt with independently. There are a variety of methods through which eutrophication and pollutants interact. Eutrophication may result in greater pollutant scavenging by dissolved organic carbon (DOC), higher sedimentation of contaminants, and increased absorption in the food chain due to dilution of toxins in increasing volumes of biomass. The use of mathematical modelling in the research and analysis of the impacts of eutrophication on aquatic populations has proven to be quite beneficial. Several scholars have developed mathematical models in this direction. (J.B. Shukla, A.K. Misra, Peeyush Chandra 2008; Anita Chaturvedi, O P Misra, 2010; O. P. Misra, Divya Chaturvedi, 2016)

Recently, Karydis [1] explained that, the causes that produce eutrophication vary from one lake to the next, dependent on the environment in which the lake is situated. From past decade, numerous researchers have been discussed the quantitative assessment of eutrophication [2-5]. The key new approach to artificial intelligence is Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). Based on the input that travels through the network during the learning process, whether externally or internally, ANNs are evolutionarily versatile in a variety of conditions. To increase the performance of a Multilayer Perceptron network, an ANN uses the Back Propagation (BP) approach. The back-propagation algorithm, first discovered by Paul Werbos in 1974, was rediscovered by Rumelhart and Parker. The back-propagation strategy has been often employed as a learning mechanism in feed forward multilayer neural networks since its rediscovery. The Levenberg-Marquardt technique is a revolutionary convergent stability strategy for ANNs that can solve a broad variety of liquid flow complications mathematically. Recently, Shoaib et al. [6-8] used the ANN based Levenberg-Marquardt technique to discuss thermal characteristics of different fluid flow problems. Raja et al. [9-10] used the ANN based Levenberg-Marquardt technique to discuss dynamics of entropy optimized different nanofluidic systems.

To handle numerically structural, hydrodynamic, and multiphysics issues, finite element techniques are frequently employed. The scientists and engineers can mathematically model and numerically solve exceedingly complicated issues, hence the approaches are widely employed. Engineering analyses are carried out to evaluate designs, whereas scientific analyses are carried out primarily to gain intuition into and ideally, forecast natural events. The ability to forecast how a design will operate, as well as if and how a natural phenomenon will occur, is very valuable: Designs may be made more cost-effective, safer and knowledge of and predictions about nature can aid in catastrophe prevention, for example. As a result, using the finite element approach enhances our lives significantly. Finite element techniques are undoubtedly employed for the analysis of every significant engineering design today, as well as in almost every discipline of science. Commercial finite element programmes are currently

generally utilized to implement the approach. These applications are used to tackle very complicated problems on personal computers, workstations and mainframes. While finite element methods were originally created to study structures and solids, they are currently used to study multiphysics problems like fluid flows with fluid–structure interactions [11-13]. By using finite element analysis, numerous researchers explored the effects in Lake Eutrophication [14-18]. The main goal of this analysis is to deliver a brief study that summarizes major causes, and effects of lake eutrophication in order to propose a better solution for a lake that has been eutrophicated due to an overabundance of algae and other biological species induced by nutrient flow from home drainage, water runoff, and other sources, as well as nutrients created from detritus. The variables bilinear interactions such as cumulative nutrient concentrations, algal (phytoplankton) and zooplankton population densities, detritus density, and dissolved oxygen concentration are addressed.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

We consider a lake that has been eutrophicated due to an overabundance of algae and other biological species induced by nutrient flow from home drainage, water runoff, and other sources, as well as nutrients created from detritus. The variables bilinear interactions like cumulative nutrient concentrations, algal (phytoplankton) and zooplankton population densities, detritus density, and dissolved oxygen concentration are addressed. We believe that home drainage as well as runoff from agricultural areas provides varied nutrients to the water body. The demise of algae and zooplankton may also provide these nutrients. We presume that the phytoplankton population is entirely reliant on nutrients and that it is consumed by the predatory zooplankton. Furthermore, it is believed that the oxygen quantity dissolved in the water body rises at a constant rate due to diffusion, etc. Let 'n' represent the cumulative concentration of different nutrients, 'a' represent algae density, 'F' represents zooplankton population density, 'S' represents detritus density, and 'C' represent dissolved oxygen concentration (DO). We assume that the cumulative rate of nutrient flow from outside the water body into the aquatic system is 'q,' a constant that is depleted at a rate of $(\alpha_2 n)$ owing to natural processes. It is also believed that detritus has a cumulative growth rate of nutrients of $(\pi_1 \delta S)$ and that nutrient depletion by algae is proportional to both the density of algae and the concentration of nutrient (na) . As algae is supposed to be completely reliant on nutrients, its growth rate is proportional to (na) . The natural depletion rate of algae is considered to be proportional to its density 'a', while the rate of depletion owing to crowding or food use in the water body is proportional to a^2 . The rate of depletion of algae by its predator zooplankton is assumed to be proportional to (aF) , and thus zooplankton growth is proportional to (aF) . The natural depletion rate of zooplankton is considered to be proportional to its density F, while the rate of depletion owing to crowding is assumed to be proportional to F^2 . Because some natural depletions of algae and zooplankton are converted into detritus, its growth rate is proportional to 'a' and F, and its natural depletion rate is related to 'S.' we assume that the rate of growth of

dissolved oxygen from diverse sources is constant (qC), and that the rate of natural depletion is proportional to its concentration (C). It is also thought that algae's growth rate is directly related to a , and that detritus's conversion into nutrients is directly related to its concentration 'S'. The following is the structure of the mathematical model of the governing system with the five state variables indicated above:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dn}{dt} &= q - \pi_1 \delta s + \alpha_2 n - gn^2 \\ \frac{da}{dt} &= \theta_1 \beta_1 na - v_1 a^2 + \alpha_1 a \\ \frac{dc}{dt} &= q_c + v_1 c - \lambda_1 a \\ \frac{ds}{dt} &= \pi_2 \alpha_3 a + \pi_3 \alpha_4 F - v_3 s \\ \frac{dF}{dt} &= \lambda_2 nF + \alpha_3 F - \lambda_3 F^2\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

With initial conditions

$$a(0) = a_0 > 0, n(0) = n_0 > 0, c(0) = C_0 > 0, s(0) = s_0 > 0, f(0) = f_0 > 0$$

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \theta_1, \theta_2, \delta_1, \delta$ are proportionality constant which are positive.

α_i 's Are depletion rate coefficients.

$\lambda_1, \beta_1, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \delta, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ Are proportionality constants which are positive.

v_1, v_3 Are coefficients corresponding to crowding.

π_1, π_2, π_3 Are functional proportionality constants.

q is the cumulative rate of discharge of nutrients into the water body outside.

q_c is the rate of growth of DO by various sources (assumed as constant).

Initial conditions are assumed as $a(0) = a_0 > 0, n(0) = n_0 > 0, C(0) = C_0 > 0, S(0) = S_0 > 0, F(0) = F_0 > 0$.

Where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \theta_1, \theta_2, \delta$ and δ_1 are positive proportionality constants and α_i 's are positive depletion rate coefficients, β_{10} and β_{20} are coefficients corresponding to crowding of algae and zooplankton populations respectively. π_0, π_1 and π_2 are the fractional proportionality constants and the value lies between 0 and 1 ($0 < \pi_0, \pi_1, \pi_2 < 1$). q is the cumulative rate of discharge of nutrients into the water body outside and q_c is the rate of growth of DO by various sources (assumed as constant).

3. FINITE ELEMENT METHOD (FEM) SOLUTION

The ensuing coupled nonlinear initial value problem is solved numerically. The FEM is utilized to solve nonlinear coupled governing equations. The equation (1) – (5) are solved iteratively to

obtain the cumulative concentration of different nutrients (n), algae density (a), zooplankton population density(F), detritus density(S) and dissolved oxygen concentration(C). To ensure that the findings are accurate, the error level of the solution is set at 0.0001. When the above-mentioned error threshold is reached, i.e., the difference between the previous iteration and the present iteration for all variables at all nodes, the iterative process comes to an end. Linear elements with two nodes are considered to analyze the variations in the cumulative concentration of different nutrients (n), algae density (a), fish population density (F), detritus density (S) and dissolved oxygen concentration(C). Nodes are linked together with lines to form a mesh structure. In order to get the findings, 60 mesh points are taken into account.

Figure 1. Variation in 'F' and 'C' with respect to t for different values of 'q'

Figure 2. Variation in 'a' and 'S' with respect to t for different values of 'q'

Figure 1 (a) – (b) and Figure 2 (a) – (b) illustrates the effect of 'q' that is, the cumulative rate of nutrient flow from outside the water body into the aquatic system on fish population density

(F), dissolved oxygen concentration(C), algae density (a) and detritus density (S) with respect to time 't'. As the value of cumulative rate of nutrient flow from outside the water body into the aquatic system that is, 'q' increases, the zooplankton population, and density of algae also the detritus density increases in the aquatic system but the dissolved oxygen concentration decreases in the aquatic system.

4. ANN MODEL:

In recent years, the use of artificial intelligence techniques like neural networks (ANN) has become a major study topic. ANN model is implemented for the estimation of the algae density, detritus and zooplankton along with dissolved oxygen concentration in the aquatic system; this is the first research of its kind, and as such, it should be regarded as groundbreaking. ANN model has been established by utilizing the pertinent parameters data set attained by numerical approaches that is, by finite element method. Four, five, three and four neurons have been utilized in the ANN models hidden layer developed for the overall density estimation of algae, dissolved oxygen concentration, detritus density and zooplankton density in the aquatic system respectively. 80% of the data utilized in the progress of the multilayer perceptron network, 10% of the data has been utilized for training the model and 10% for testing.

Figure 3. The structures of the developed ANN model for a) algae density b) dissolved oxygen concentration c) detritus density d) zooplankton density

Figure 3 displays the number of layers in the ANN model and also the number of neurons in the hidden layers. As seen in Figure 3, two layers are there in the neural network model in which one is the hidden layer and the other one is the output layer. In the hidden layer 4 neurons are taken for estimating the algae density, 5 neurons are taken for the estimation of dissolved oxygen concentration in the aquatic system, three neurons are taken for estimating detritus density and 4 neurons are taken for estimating zooplankton density and the major affecting parameters like nutrients concentration in the aquatic system 'n', cumulative rate of nutrient flow from outside the water body into the aquatic system 'q' and the time variable are taken as input parameters which shows the considerable effect on these output parameters.

The multilayer perceptron network is trained using the Bayesian regularization approach, which corrects the weight and refraction values using the Levenberg-Marquardt optimization. The MSE, coefficient of determination (R), and margin of deviation (MoD) measures were utilized to analyse the ANNs' estimate performance. Below are the mathematical formulae used to calculate the performance characteristics?

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)} - X_{ANN(i)})^2 \quad (25)$$

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)} - X_{ANN(i)})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)})^2}} \quad (26)$$

$$MoD(\%) = \left(\frac{X_{\text{exp}} - X_{ANN}}{X_{\text{exp}}} \right) \times 100 \quad (27)$$

Mathematical models were made using the MATLAB program.

Table 1: Performance parameters of the ANN models

Parameters	MSE	R	MoD
A	1.5E-15	1	0.0001
C	1.43E-14	0.97153	0.02
S	1.67E-15	0.9948	0.005
F	1.54E-14	0.98034	0.01

Figure 5. Comparison of algae density ANN model with FEM data

Figure 6. Comparison of dissolved oxygen concentration level ANN model with finite element results

Figure 7. Comparison of detritus density ANN model with finite element results

Figure 8. Comparison of zooplankton density ANN model with finite element result

Figures 5–8 show the ANN model predictions compared to the target data, which is the FEM data, and the model's performance has been evaluated. The performance metrics MSE, R, and MoD have all been computed and examined as well. The ANN models MSE values developed for the density of algae, dissolved oxygen concentration, detritus density and zooplankton density are calculated. The study's outcomes revealed that the built ANN models can generate accurate predictions.

5. CONCLUSION

A lake that has been eutrophicated due to an overabundance of algae and other biological species induced by nutrient flow from home drainage, water runoff, and other sources, as well as nutrients created from detritus is considered in this study. The variables bilinear interactions such as cumulative nutrient concentrations, algal (phytoplankton) and zooplankton population densities, detritus density, and dissolved oxygen concentration are addressed. ANN model has been developed by using the data set of pertinent parameters obtained by finite element method. The MSE values for the ANN models developed for the density of algae, dissolved oxygen concentration, detritus density and zooplankton density are calculated. The study's outcomes revealed that the built ANN models can generate accurate predictions.

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